

Ideas in Action

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Introduction

Violence among human beings is not a new concept; it is associated with relationships for a long time. Violence can be of different forms such as acts of physical, sexual, psychological and economical abused treatments, without any boundaries of age, race, civilization, cultural values and geographical locations. Violence does not only refer to physical aggression; but also incorporates emotional and psychological maltreatments that can be equally harmful as physical violence for the victims (Abramsky et al., 2011). The acts of violence have acutely negative impacts on social wellbeing of individuals, family structures, children's upbringing and development of youth. It can potentially confine the rights of individuals to be implicated in a healthy societal existence.

In recent years, the occurrence of violence has increased to a significant and noticeable extent. This radical increase in violence is subjected to a number of reasons and factors. Though violence is an extremely inhumane and destructive act; yet it is somehow inevitable in relationships among human beings (Anderson, 2014). Therefore, this paper will attempt to assess this argument that violence is an inevitable feature of human relationships. Additionally, the paper will discuss the intermediate factors that are responsible for occurrence of violence at individual, social, or at a global level.

Discussion

There are different perspectives and opinions on the concept of violence that are prevailing among the present day society. However, there is a wide agreement on the idea that violence is an inhumane act; no matter how it is carried out; the consequences are always damaging and negative (Elbert et al., 2010). Violence among human relationships is subjected to various reasons that gradually piles up and eventually result in the form of violence. First of all, it has been shown through previous researches and studies that individuals who faced violent behaviors in their childhood are likely to develop an intention to practice the same in the coming years of their lives. This statement can be linked with the findings of a research study, which highlighted that individuals who faced childhood maltreatment and abusive acts are greatly expected to grow into adults who abuse (Guo et al., 2008). The approximated calculation is that between 30 to 40 percent of individuals who faced child abuse will develop into individuals who would abuse themselves.

Moreover, violence in human relationships is also an outcome of gender discrimination and uneven authority status among men and women that makes it an enveloping experience. Domestic violence is an ideal example in this aspect, which is based on the differences among different genders. However, the victims of domestic violence are mostly the women; who become sufferers of violence resulting from personal or collective violent behaviours (Jensen, n.d). The trends of domestic violence are not restricted to developing countries, but developed countries are also experiencing this terrible issue. Regardless of development in strategies and legislative procedures, domestic violence is still one of the top human rights problems at a global level.

Violence in human relationships is also derived from psychological factors; such as depression, lack of trust, dishonesty, and infighting (Seckan, 2012). These factors eventually make human beings to involve in violent actions; therefore making violence an unavoidable feature. Violence against children is also a dreadful act; which is also refereed as child abuse. Children often become victims of aggression and emotional abuse resulting from damaged family structures and poor parenting (Elbert et al., 2010). This sort of violence can be observed when individuals who suffered from ill-treatment in their own upbringing, or experienced violence amid their families, parents, caregivers; receives an opportunity to employ physical castigation as a way of parenting their own children.

At a global level, example of violence can be observed in acts such as human trafficking; which is a sadistic form of violence among human beings. Human trafficking is an illegal and criminal type of contemporary slavery that has emerged as a money-making business across the globe (Abramsky et al., 2011). It is mainly the process of buying and selling of human beings for earnings, who are later obliged to perform unwilling actions such as pleading, indisposed servitude and exploitation for sexual purposes. This terrible business signifies the harsh effects of violence among human beings that can be extremely damaging for physical, mental and emotional well-being.

Conclusion

In the light of the facts discussed in the paper; it can be ascertain that argument implying that violence is an inevitable feature of human relationships is acceptable. The reasons for concurring with this argument are the facts discussed in the paper; which implies various sources that are responsible for developing and deriving violent behaviors among human beings.

Violence among human relationships varies from physical to emotional, child abuse to domestic violence, and from communal to a global level. However, it is necessary to adopt policies and approaches that can alleviate this terrible act as the consequences are highly damaging; and in some cases, might lead towards self-abuse or even suicidal attempts.

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